

Neutron Stars and the EOS of Dense Matter

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Summary

Our history and knowledge of both neutron stars and the nucleus has progressed incrementally over the past 90 years since the original work of Oppenheimer and others. The main recent change has been the discovery that neutron stars can be fairly massive (about two solar masses) with a radius of around ten km. The effect of most changes to the EOS - such as moderately changing the stiffness or limiting the sound speed - is within the ten percent uncertainty of the data. For example, the maximum mass $m=M=m_1$ which peaks as a function of the scaled radius r/r_{SW} does not vary beyond these limits. The effect of limiting the speed of sound in neutron matter to $0.5c$ is to reduce the mass (2.2 to 1.9 solar masses for $K=274$ or 1.9 to 1.8 for $K=202$) or change the radius of the neutron star by less than ten percent. A symmetry in several quantities across models or EOSs is identified. A peak or hook in both the mass curve and the binding energy curve is identified; this limits the maximum mass of a neutron star as a domain of instability is approached. However it is unlikely that much more can be learned without high

precision data from neutron stars and nuclear experiments. The recent NICER data indicates the beginning of this era.

Introduction

Over the past 40 years [1] there has been some progress [2] in the understanding of the equation of state (EOS) of ultra-dense matter. The seminal work was done long ago by Tolman [3] and Oppenheimer [4] and appears in most textbooks [5]. Nevertheless, a variety of models [6] continue to proliferate some with exotic features such as with cores of strange matter, quark matter, or dark matter. Some have even proposed changes to General Relativity itself because of both the need to connect more fundamentally with quantum physics and due to new cosmology data.

Our Investigation

We have undertaken a relatively straightforward investigation using the TOV equation

- $$dp/dr = -G m \rho / r^2 (1 + 4 \pi p r^3 / m c^2) (1 + p / \rho c^2) / (1 - 2 GM / r c^2)$$

and a few simple models. We shall refer to the three factors in the TOV equation as: pressure $(1 + 4 \pi p r^3 / m c^2)$, enthalpy $((\rho c^2 + p) / \rho c^2)$, and Schwarzschild $(1 - 2 GM / r c^2)$ factors.

The Schwarzschild (or time retardation or length contraction or metric) factor of course contains the Schwarzschild radius $2 G M / c^2$. When combined with the star radius this gives rise to the so-called beta factor $G M / R c^2$ which appears in the Tolman, Maximum Uniform, Buchdahl, and many other simple models. We use CGS units though some quantities are clearly dimensionless.

The main two models (soft $K=202$ and medium $K=274$) studied here use the VUU/Skyrme type EOS [7] but with added nuclear symmetry energy [2] and subject to a limit of $1/2 \rho c^2$ at high densities. Neutron matter differs from nuclear matter in the Fermi energy degeneracy factor (2 vs. 4) and also the symmetry energy. The limit of the sound speed (phase velocity) is motivated by other investigations although some have thought [6] that dispersion or other studies might lead to a revision based on requirements for the group velocity. At lower densities the EOS reduces to simply the Fermi neutron pressure which has a known limiting behaviour of $1/3 \rho c^2$ at very high densities. Of course in the white dwarf range, this neutron star neutron pressure would become the white dwarf electron pressure. All of our calculations are performed using a fourth order Runge Kutta solver in Mathematica [8]. A fitted or unified EOS (so called SLy) and the three models (Tolman, Maximum Uniform, and Buchdahl) are used as references where appropriate. The main experimental data that is referenced is that from NICER [9].

At least four masses may be defined for a neutron star (Gratton had six [6]):

1. m_1 the Kepler mass from the mass energy density ρ
2. m_2 from the baryon mass (density)
3. m_3 from the proper baryon density
4. m_4 from the proper mass energy (density).

Some of these can be equal under certain circumstances (e.g. in the classical limit). Each proper mass includes in the integral of its calculation the factor $1/(1-2\beta)^{1/2}$ where the beta factor $Gm/r c^2$ depends on a mass $m(r)$ that increases with radius. This factor is the time retardation in the gravitational field (redshift). The first mass $m_1=m(R)=M$ is the observational mass: the star's

total mass energy (in solar masses). Combinations of these masses lead to two binding energies or mass defects, one the usual gravitational potential energy [5] $m_4 - m_3$ and the other defect energy $m_3 - m_1$ due to Iben and Touper [6].

Several radii may also be defined and appear in the literature:

- Schwarzschild gravitational radius $r_{sw} = 2 GM/c^2$
- Coordinate radius typically from the TOV equation
- Radius from the beta factor due to any mass $r = GM/(\beta c^2)$
- z shift radius $r_z = n_g r$; $\cos n_g = (1 - 2\beta)^{1/2}$
- Proper radius from integration such as integral of $dr/(1 - 2\beta(r))^{1/2}$
- Radius from Lane Emden or Tooper theta function zeroes $r = \eta/a$ where a is a scale factor
- Model specific radius, e.g. Maximum Uniform has $R = (r^3/r_{sw})^{1/2}$
- Regular vs. canonical radius, e.g. Buchdahl model has $r = R[1 - \beta + \beta \text{SINC}[\pi r/R]]/(1 - 2\beta)$

Some of these can be equal under certain circumstances (e.g. in the classical limit).

Some other observables or potentially measurable quantities that are referred to in the various figures and table are (here $r=R$):

- $r_{rsw} = r/r_{SW} = rc^2/2GM = 1/(2\beta)$
- $r_{rsn} = 4 \pi p r^3/M c^2$
- $n_{\eta} = G m \rho / (4 p r)$
- $\sigma = ((\rho c^2 + p) / \rho c^2)$

- $d_{mec} = M \rho^2 / (p/G)^{3/2}$
- $b_{rec} = (\langle p \rangle / G)^{3/2} / M \langle \rho \rangle^2$
- $GPE/m_1 = (m_4 - m_1)/m_1$ (the standard gravitational potential energy per star mass)
- $BE_T = m_3 - m_1$ (the Tooper or Iben binding energy or mass defect).

The utility of these variables is seen in our main Figure 1 as well as the other Figures 2-9.

The quantity ν is of special interest because it relates directly to the mass under certain conditions. Note that the observable $\sigma = 1 + p / \rho c^2$. For some models, the quantity $p / \rho c^2$ is a simple constant or analytic function of the parameter β . Let $\sigma^2 = p / \rho c^2$. Then we find that

- $\nu = \nu_{eta} = G m / (4 r c^2 \sigma^2)$

which means that ν_{eta} is proportional to the main mass $m = m_1 = M$. Although this seems simple - it is of historical interest from the Tooper and other models [6] - the effects of items like the EOS stiffness can then be seen more easily in the calculations and plots. See Figure 10b which is transformed thereby into Figure 10a.

In the figures $r=R$ the star radius, $p=p_c$ the central pressure, $\rho=\rho_{MEc}$ the central mass energy density, ρ_{BC} =central baryon density, and $m=M$ the star mass. See the Table for select results. Most of these quantities are defined by others, for example ν_{eta} by Tooper and also the Tooper/Iben binding energy [6].

Table. Select results for the main two EOS and reference models. ρ_C is in units of 10^{15} g/cc; r is in km; m is in solar masses.

EOS	ρ_C	r	m	$rrsw$	$rrsn$	$m4$	GPE/m	BE T
NUC274	1.32	12.1	1.93	2.12	2.15	2.4	0.243	0.27
NUC202	1.57	11.9	1.78	2.27	2.27	2.2	0.237	0.237
Tolman 7	1.55	10.9	1.70	2.17	1.88	2	0.236	0.241
SLy	2.63	10.1	2.04	1.67	4.12	2.78	0.359	0.383
Max. Uni.	1.55	8.2	1.79	1.55	1.55	2.35	0.315	0.564
pf+sym	1.82	13.9	1.25	3.77	2.89	1.44	0.153	0.053
pf	1.90	11.1	0.69	5.46	1.6	0.75	0.097	0.022

Both the Maximum Uniform and the Tolman 7 model will of course produce a larger mass with a different central density. We have also used the Buchdahl model but do not include the results in the table. The Buchdahl model tends to generate a much too large radius (about 26 km) for a two solar mass neutron star. The Bonner-Ebert spheres [6] produce even larger radii (technically infinite so they are truncated) and so are used mostly in interstellar cloud or clump modeling. The quoted SLy radius and mass, though not of central importance to this investigation, do agree with the values in the paper by Douchin and Haensel. The known exact reference models (Tolman 7, Maximum Uniform, Buchdahl) have been compared with the known formulae [6] to verify the precision of our code.

From our study it is clear that *nothing special* is needed to explain neutron star data. Both older models and newer ones give radii and masses in the range of the data, e.g. about 12 km for radius and 2 solar masses for mass in accord with NICER and other data [9].

The location of the maximal mass appears to lie on or near the central line on our main graph (see Figure 1). The black line is for reference only and indicates that the maximal mass for the two main neutron matter EOSs occurs around $r/r_{\text{SW}} = 2$ (more precisely 2.1-2.3) which corresponds to $\beta = .25$.

Curiously, most of the other models with the same variables show similar behavior; see Figures 2, 3, and 4 for a study of many of the observables of historical and current interest. This result is not substantially different from that of the Tolman 7 model or any of the unified equations of state [6]. Figure 2 shows the variables for the Maximum Uniform model. Many of the interesting observables are plotted vs. r/r_{SW} . All the Maximum Uniform curves meet around $x=1.55$ which corresponds to a $\beta = .323$. Figure 3 shows the similar result for the Tolman 7 model. Many of the interesting variables are again plotted vs. r/r_{SW} . All the Tolman 7 curves meet around $x=2.5$ which corresponds to $\beta = .20$. Figure 4 shows a similar result for the Buchdahl model. Many of the interesting variables are plotted vs. r/r_{SW} . All the Buchdahl model curves meet around $x=.5$ which corresponds to a $\beta = .10$.

This result of the symmetry or matching of these observables is easy to understand, at least in the simplest model: the Maximum Uniform where the density of the neutron star is constant

although the pressure varies (similar to our atmosphere or the ocean where the fluid weight affects the pressure). Here most of the proposed measurable quantities are simple functions of $\beta = \beta$; thus there exists a unique value of β where several or all of these are equal! The same may be seen in the Buchdahl and Tolman 7 models. For the general case of our two EOSs, there is not a known closed form function of β so that the result is just observed numerically (Figure 1 etc.).

Figure 5 shows the mass energy density profile for our main investigation. Results for the same $\rho = \rho_{ME}$ at the center are shown.

Figure 6ab (pressure) and 6cd ($dp/d\rho$) for the various models with similar central densities give an idea of how the numerical results are related. The stiffer EOS has a larger $dp/d\rho$ which by chance is comparable to the Tolman 7 values shown in Figure (6c). In Figure 6a, the softer EOS (202) has a peak mass at a higher baryon density ($1.3 \cdot 10^{15}$) than the 1.1 density found for the medium EOS (274); the central pressures thus come out about the same.

Figures 7, 8, and 9ab show four of the observable quantities with respect to the pressure factor from the text and Figure 1. For our two main neutron matter EOSs, the variable ν_{eta} again has the value about two (2.1-2.3) for the maximum mass. The plotted enthalpy variable also has value about two (interestingly for the SLy EOS as well as the Maximum Uniform EOS it is exactly 2.0). Similar results occur for the d_{mec} and b_{rec} variables.

Figure 10 shows the baryon proper mass m_3 as a function of the ν_{eta} variable. The effect of most changes to the EOS - such as moderately changing the stiffness or limiting the sound speed - is within the ten percent uncertainty of the data. See also Figure 11a for m_1 . The observable mass $m=M=m_1$ is shown as a function of the scaled radius r/r_{SW} . The effect of limiting the speed of sound in neutron matter to $.5 c^2$ is to reduce the mass of the neutron star by less than ten percent. Thus it is unlikely that much more can be learned without more and better high precision data from neutron stars and nuclear experiments. The recent NICER data [9] indicates the beginning of this era.

The measured binding energy from SN1987a of .17 solar masses is right in the middle of our calculated binding energy curves Figure 12abcd. The form of this binding energy curve also relates to the fact that in the simpler models the binding energy is a function of the parameter β . Figure 12c explicitly shows how closely the binding energy is related to the simple β expansions for the two primary neutron matter EOSs.

The hook or candy cane behavior seen in the two figures (11a and 12d) for the main EOSs perhaps explains the so called gap in neutron star masses from three to five solar masses. This hook has appeared in other work [6,10] but without this interpretation. As noted by Tooper [6], the non-linearities in the field equations (and resulting TOV differential equation) cause the fall off. Gratton [6] has also shown that singular points and oscillatory behaviour may exist in some models; he did this via plots using a system of homologous coordinates (see Figures 13 and 14 for these graphs for our models). In the classical domain, Bonnor [6] also found long ago in

standard pV curves trajectories that spiral around a singular point. We do not find evidence for these types of singular points from Bonnor or Gratton [6].

The limiting mass [11,12] for a neutron star with about 10 km radius also follows directly from the TOV equation with $\beta=4/9$ and is three solar masses.

Conclusions

The effect of most changes to the EOS - such as moderately changing the stiffness or limiting the sound speed - is within the ten percent uncertainty of the data. For example, the maximum mass $m=M=m_1$ which peaks as a function of the scaled radius r/r_{SW} does not vary beyond these limits. The effect of limiting the speed of sound in neutron matter to $.5 c^2$ is to reduce the mass (2.2 to 1.9 solar masses for $K=274$ or 1.9 to 1.8 for $K=202$) or change the radius of the neutron star by less than ten percent. Thus it is unlikely that much more can be learned without more better high precision data from neutron stars and nuclear experiments. The recent NICER data indicates the beginning of this era. A symmetry in several quantities cross models or EOSs is identified. A peak or hook in both the mass curve and the binding energy curve is also identified; this limits the maximum mass of a neutron star as a domain of instability is approached.

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References

1. *The Boltzmann Equation at the Borderline*, J. Molitoris et. al., *Phys. Rep.* 243 (1994) 1-124..
See also: Molitoris, J. and Stoecker, H. (1985), *Can We Extract the Nuclear Equation of State?*, Phase Space Approach to Nuclear Dynamics, Singapore: World Scientific (1985) 134-152.
2. *The EOS of Hot Dense Matter*, J. Lattimer and M. Prakash, 2015. See also: *Neutron Stars*, J. Lattimer, 33rd SLAC Summer Institute, 2005. A more recent update is: *Neutron Stars and Nuclear Matter*, J. Lattimer, *Ann. Rev. Nucl. Part. Sci.* 2021 (71) 433-464. Further: *The Nuclear Symmetry Energy*, M. Baldo and G. Burgio, *Prog. Part. Nucl. Phys.* 2016 (91) 203-258 and *Constraints on Nuclear Symmetry Energy Parameters*, J. Lattimer, 2023, arXIV: 2301.03666v1 as well as *Nuclear and Neutron Star Matter*, D. Lonardoni et. al., *Phys. Rev. Res.* 2 (2020) 022033R. Also: *Studies of the EOS of Nuclear Matter*, P. Russotto et. al., 2023, arXIV:2302.01453v1 and *New EOS in Simulations of Core Collapse Supernovae*, M. Hempel et. al. *ApJ* 748 (2012) 70 as well as *Nuclear Matter Calculations*, .H. Moeinia and G. Bordbar, 2022, arXIV:2204.07468v1. More on the symmetry energy: *Forms of the Symmetry Energy*, I. Bednarek, J. Sladkowski, J. Syska, *Symmetry* 2020 12 (6) 898 and *Incompressibility in Finite Nuclei*, J. Stone, N. Stone, S. Moszkowski, *Phys. Rev. C* (2014) as well as *Nuclear Matter Properties*, X. Vinas, P. Bano, Z. Nail, T. Rotary, *Symmetry* 2024 (16) 215.
3. *Static Solutions of Einstein Field Equations*, R. Tolman, *Phys. Rev.* 55 (374) 1939.
4. *On Massive Neutron Cores*, J. Oppenheimer and G. Volkoff, *Phys. Rev.* 55 (374) 1939.

5. Gravitation, C. Misner, K. Thorne, J. Wheeler, W.H. Freeman, San Francisco, 1973. See also: Relativity, R. Tolman, Oxford: Clarendon, 1934 and NY: Dover, 1987 and Stars and Relativity, Y. Zeldovich and I. Novikov, Chicago, Univ. Press, 1971. More recently: Neutron Stars, P. Haensel, A. Potekhin, D. Yakovlev, NY: Springer, 2007. A timeless classic: Principles of Stellar Evolution, D. Clayton, NY: McGraw Hill, 1968.
6. *General Relativity Fluid Spheres*, H. Buchdahl, Ap. J. 1967 (147) p. 310. See also: *A Unified EOS of Dense Matter*, F. Douchin and P. Haensel, Astro. and Astrophys. 380 (2001) 151-167. Further: *Massive Stars*, I. Iben, Ap. J. 1963 (138) 1090 and *General Relativistic Spheres*, R. Tooper, Ap. J. 1964 (140) 434; *Boyle's Law and Gravitational Instability*, W. Bonnor, (1956) MNRAS.116.351B Royal Astron. Society; *Numerical Results on the Equilibrium of Highly Collapsed Bodies*, L. Gratton, TSRA conference (1969) Gordon and Breach/ NASA Astrophys. Data System. For a very readable account see: *A Modern View of the EOS*, G. Burgio et. al., Symmetry 2021 (13) 400. One of the many SLy models is given in Table C1, page 528 from CERN backmatter online files.
7. *Further Evidence from Transverse Momentum Analysis*, J. Molitoris and H. Stoecker, Phys. Rev. C (1985) 346. See also: *Reconciliation of Neutron Star Masses*, N. Glendenning and S. Moszkowski, PRL 1991 (67) 2414. *The Effective Nuclear Potential*, T. Skyrme, Nucl. Phys. 9 (1959) 615-634. *Elliptic and Quadrangular Flow of Protons*, S. Lan, Z. Liu, L. Liu, S. Shi, Universe 2025 (11) 27.
8. *The Mathematica Book*, Wolfram, S., IL: Wolfram Research, 1998-2020.
9. NICER and other data reported in T. Salmi et. al., 2024, arXIV:2406.14466v2. See also: M. Miller et. al., *Mass and Radius from NICER Data*, Astro. J. 2019 (887) L24. Other exciting

recent data: *Discovery of 26 new Galactic Radio Transients* by MeerTRAP, J. Turner et. al., arXiv:2501.08224v1 (2025). Some heavy ion data: *Results of the ASY-EOS Experiment*, P. Russotto et. Al., 2016, arXiv:1608.04332v2.

10. *Neutron Stars and Nuclear Matter*, J. Lattimer, Ann. Rev. Nucl. Part. Sci. 2021 (71) 433-464.
11. C. Rhoades and R. Ruffini, PRL 32 (324) 1974 and more recently: *Impact of the PSR J0740+6620 Radius Constraint*, I. Legred et. al. (2021).
12. *Causal Limit of Neutron Star Maximum Mass*, A. Astashenok et. al., 2021, arXiv: 2103.04144v2. See also the textbook: page 345 in Gravitation and Spacetime, H. Ohanian, NY: Norton, 1976.

Figures

Figure 1. Pressure factor vs. the star radius scaled by the Schwarzschild radius. The black line is for reference only and indicates that the maximal mass for the two main neutron matter EOSs occurs around $r/r_{\text{SW}} = 2$ (more precisely 2.1-2.3) which corresponds to $\beta = 0.25$.

Figure 2. Maximum Uniform model. Many of the interesting variable are plotted vs. r/r_{SW} . All

the curves meet around $x=1.55$ which corresponds to a $\beta=.323$.

Figure 3. Tolman 7 model. Many of the interesting variable are plotted vs. r/r_{SW} . All the curves

meet around $x=2.5$ which corresponds to a $\beta=.20$.

Figure 4. Buchdahl model. Many of the interesting variables are plotted vs. r/r_{SW} . All the curves meet around $x=.5$ which corresponds to a $\beta=.10$.

Figure 5a. Mass energy density profile for our main investigation. Results for the same rhoME at the center are shown.

Figure 5b. Results for a lower central density are shown. Mass energy density profile for our main two models compared to reference models. Results for the same rhoME at the center are shown.

Figure 6a. Pressure for the various models for similar central densities.

Figure 6b. Pressure for the various models for a lower central density (see Figure 5b).

Figure 6c. $dp/d\rho$ for the various models (density scaled by central densities).

Figure 6d. $dp/d\rho$ for the various models (density not scaled) and for the lower densities of Figure 5b.

Figure 7. Ten times nueta1 = $10 G m \rho / (4 p r) = 2.5 G m \rho / (p r)$

Figure 8. Enthalpy.

Figure 9a. The dmec variable is plotted.

Figure 9b. The brec variable is examined. We also show two other neutron matter EOSs plus a simple polytropic (exponent 3) EOS. Note in all cases that the neutron star observable mass does no significantly exceed two solar masses.

Figure 10a. Baryon proper mass as a function of the nueta variable.

Figure 10b. Baryon proper mass as a function of the main mass $m=M=m_1$. The separation of the coincident curves is improved by the nueta variable in Figure 10a.

Figure 11a. The observable mass $m=M=m_1$ as a function of the scaled radius r/r_{SW} . The effect of limiting the speed of sound in neutron matter to $.5 c^2$ is to reduce the radius of the neutron star by less than ten percent.

Alternate figure

Figure 11b. Speed of sound squared scaled by c^2 for the various models at or about the peak maximum density for each model.

Figure 12a. Binding energy (GPE).

Figure 12b. Binding energy related to the pressure factor.

Figure 12c. Binding energy related to beta expansions.

Alternate figure with Buchdahl added

Alternate figure with two more EOSs and Tooper polytrope added.

Figure 12d. Tooper Binding energy as a function of beta.

Alternate figure with Buchdahl added.

More EOSs.

Figure 13. The evolution of the TOV equation for the various models is illustrated by the use of homologous coordinates (see Gratton [6]). The horizontal axis ordinate value of 3 corresponds to the center of the star.

Figure 14. Zoom on the previous figure. The evolution of the TOV equation for the various models is illustrated by the use of homologous coordinates (see Gratton [6]).

